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In 1993, KDML 105 was tested under the 16th International Rainfed Lowland Rice Observational Nursery of INGER as accession no. ET23263 (IRRI, Philippines).

KDML 105 is photoperiod-sensitive and may be harvested with other winter rice varieties. It has been recommended for cultivation in semideepwater ecosystems in the North Bank Plain Zone of Assam in 1998. KDML 105 exhibited moderate tolerance for major rice diseases. The incidence of rice stem borers and rice hispa in KDML 105 was more than that in Kolajoha and Panikekoa (14.4% stem and 4.6% leaf damage by stem borers and hispa, respectively). Under 8 mo of storage, KDML 105 exhibited 11% damage in grains due to rice weevil *Sitophilus oryzae*. Kernel softness and aroma may have attracted the insects in storage.

KDML 105 has slender grains of 9.8 × 2.8-mm dimensions and a 1000-grain weight of 25.3 g (Table 2). The kernels are soft and off-white and have a strong aroma. In an organoleptic test, 80% of a panel thought that KDML 105 was equivalent to the best Joha variety of Assam, 30% thought it was superior to Joha, and 35% said it was equivalent to Mahsuri. Cooked KDML 105 is sticky and 75% thought that the variety is unique and excellent for rice dishes such as polao, kheer, and frumenty.

KDML 105 is fast expanding in the semideepwater ecosystem as scented winter rice in Assam.

Table 1. Yield of KDML 105, Kolajoha, and Panikekoa in Assam, India, 1995-97.

Year	Location	District	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)		
			KDML 105	Kolajoha	Panikekoa
1995	Garumuria	Lakhimpur	3.4	2.4	1.8
	Gharmora	Lakhimpur	6.0	3.0	-
1996	Garumuria 1	Lakhimpur	3.0	2.2	2.8
	Garumuria 2	Lakhimpur	4.4	2.6	2.5
	Garumuria 3	Lakhimpur	1.9	-	0.9
	Gharmora	Lakhimpur	3.5	2.7	-
	Kuwari-Pukhuri	Jorhat	5.4	3.1	-
	Borigaon	Jorhat	5.8	3.0	-
	Pooled av		4.2	2.8	3.1

Table 2. Characteristics of KDML 105, Assam, 1997.

Characteristic	Remarks
<i>Plant</i>	
Type	Tall, nonlodging, semideepwater
Height (cm)	147.0
Photosensitivity	Photoperiod-sensitive
Flowering time	Late October
<i>Duration</i>	
Direct-sown	March-December
Transplanted	June-December
<i>Panicle</i>	
Type	Compact
Length (cm)	24.7
Grains panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	180.6
Sterility (%)	17.2
<i>Grains</i>	
Length (mm)	9.8
Breadth (mm)	2.8
L/B	3.6
Test weight (g, 1000 seeds ⁻¹)	25.3
<i>Yield (t ha⁻¹)</i>	
Direct-seeded	1.9-3.5
Transplanted	3.0-6.0

Sudhir, a progeny of FR13A

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FR13A was identified as an excellent source of submergence tolerance (HilleRisLambers et al 1986). It has been used by many breeders for transferring

submergence tolerance gene(s) into modern varieties. Sudhir is perhaps the first variety that used FR13A as a parent; it was developed from the cross FR13A/Biraj at

the RRS in 1981. The male parent, Biraj, an X-ray mutant of OC 1393 released in 1982, has very good regeneration capacity, good grain quality, tolerance for

drought at the reproductive stage, and soft straw, which is preferred for cattle feed.

The All-India Rice Workshop in 1994 recommended Sudhir for the semideep water (40-70 cm) areas of West Bengal, Assam, Bihar, and Uttar Pradesh based on its performance in national trials (Table 1). Accordingly, the Indian Council of Agricultural Research (ICAR) approved and recommended the variety for release in 1996.

Sudhir (CN718-8-21-10) was first nominated to the national trial in 1989 as IET10543. In 1990, it ranked first at Pusa, second at Ghagrahat, and third in overall mean (2.6 t ha⁻¹) in seven locations. The following year, the variety ranked third at Ghagrahat and fifth in overall mean (2.3 t ha⁻¹) over 11 locations. In 1992, it ranked second both at Faizabad and in overall mean over 11 locations with 3.6 t ha⁻¹ yield. Sudhir ranked first at Ghagrahat during 1993. The variety had 21%, 25%, 29%, and 40% higher yield than Rajashree, Sabita, Tilakkachari, and Utkal Prabha when tested over 8, 22, 7, and 17 locations, respectively (Table 1).

Sudhir has higher head rice recovery and better tolerance for diseases and pests than national check Sabita (Table 2). Some 6.5 quintals (650 kg) of seeds have already been distributed to 130 farmers through the Central Sector Minikit (5-kg kit) program of ICAR during 1996-98 to determine farmers' reactions. Most farmers have accepted the variety.

Reference

HilleRisLambers D, Gomosta AR, Kupkanchanakul T. 1986. Screening for submergence tolerance. In: Progress in rainfed lowland rice. Manila, Philippines: International Rice Research Institute. p 177-190.

Sudhir, a progeny of FR13A, has higher head rice recovery and better tolerance for diseases and pests than the national check.

Table 1. Performance of Sudhir (CN718-8-21-10) in different trials, 1989-96.

Year	Trial	Site	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)			Maximum water depth (cm)	
			Sudhir	Rajashree	Sabita		CD (0.05)
<i>Eastern India Rainfed Lowland shuttle breeding</i>							
1996	G × E ^a	CRRI, Cuttack	3.7	3.1	2.8	0.8	Below 50
		Masodha, UP	3.5	2.8	2.8	0.4	Below 50
		Patna, Bihar	4.9	4.6	4.6	1.4	Below 50
		Titabar, Assam	3.9	1.9	2.4	0.6	Below 50
1995	G × E	CRRI, Cuttack	3.8	2.5	3.8	0.9	Below 50
		Patna, Bihar	3.3	2.6	2.5	0.6	Below 50
		Pusa, Bihar	3.3	3.5	1.4	0.7	Below 50
		Ranital, Orissa	2.5	NA ^b	2.2	NA	Below 50
		Titabar, Assam	2.8	2.5	2.6	0.7	Below 50
<i>National Trial for Rainfed Lowland (semideepwater)</i>							
<i>Utkal Prabha</i>							
1993	AVT-SDW ^c	Karimanj, Assam	3.7	3.7	3.4	0.2	NA
		Faizabad, UP	3.4	2.3	1.9	0.6	NA
		Patna, Bihar	3.3	2.3	2.7	0.8	NA
		Chinsurah, WB	2.6	1.6	1.8	0.5	75
		Ghagrahat, UP	2.4	1.2	2.0	0.5	55
1992	AVT-SDW	Karimanj, Assam	3.8	3.5	3.5	0.5	NA
		Faizabad, UP	4.1	2.0	2.4	0.9	NA
		Ghagrahat, UP	2.0	1.2	1.5	0.6	NA
		Sabour, Bihar	2.5	2.3	2.5	0.3	NA
		Chinsurah, WB	3.8	2.3	3.3	0.5	65
1991	AVT-SDW	Canning, WB	2.6	2.1	2.2	0.5	NA
		Ghagrahat, UP	2.9	1.3	2.1	0.8	NA
		Ranital, Orissa	3.0	1.8	2.4	0.4	NA
		Tilakkachari					
1990	IVT-SDW ^d	Pusa, Bihar	2.5	2.2	1.4	0.7	50
		Sabour, Bihar	3.7	3.2	3.7	1.0	NA
		Ghagrahat, UP	2.4	1.2	0.4	0.7	NA
		Chinsurah, WB	2.3	1.8	0.8	0.4	50
		1989	PVT-5 ^e	Sabour, Bihar	4.1	NA	3.8
		Chinsurah, WB	2.4	NA	3.0	1.1	50
		Ghagrahat, UP	2.5	NA	1.5	1.2	60

^aGenotype × environment interaction. ^bNot available. ^cAVT-SDW = advanced variety trial-semideepwater. ^dIVT-SDW = initial variety trial-semideep water. ^ePVT = preliminary variety trial-5; UP = Uttar Pradesh, WB = West Bengal.

Table 2. Characteristics of Sudhir and check Sabita.

Character	Sudhir	Sabita
Plant height (cm)	150	160
Duration to 50% flowering (d)	120	120, Photoperiod-sensitive
Tillers m ⁻² (no.)	170	175
Panicle length (cm)	30	26
Weight (g)	27.8	31.9
Grain length (mm)	10.1	10.9
Grain width (mm)	2.7	2.9
Grain L/W	3.7	3.7
Kernel length (mm)	6.8	7.3
Kernel breadth (mm)	2.1	2.2
Kernel L/B	3.2	3.3
Kernel shape	Long slender	Long slender
Hulling (%)	77.6	77.5
Milling (%)	69.5	66.4
Head rice (%)	65.6	39.4
Alkali value	6.7	6.0
Amylose content (%)	27.4	30.6
Tolerance	RTD, BI, ShR, GLH, LF, GB ^a	BI
Moderate tolerance	BB, SB ^b	ShB, SB
Av yield (t ha ⁻¹)	3.1 (29) ^c	2.5 (250) ^c
Potential yield (t ha ⁻¹)	5.2	6.2
Harvest index	0.4	0.4

^aRTD = rice tungro disease, BI = blast, ShR = sheath rot, GLH = green leafhopper, LF = leaf folder, and GB = gandhi bug. ^bBB = bacterial blight, SB = stem borer, and ShB = sheath blight. ^cNumbers in parentheses indicate number of locations tested.